

Integrating Audio-based Interactions and Large Language Models into Ambient Assisted Living Environments

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Abstract. Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) environments have received increasing interest in the last decade. One of the aspects behind such an interest is population ageing, which introduces societal, economical and technological challenges. Nevertheless, the recent advancements in the latter fields, paired with the sophistication of Artificial Intelligence, IoT, and communication systems, leverage the provision of systems to improve individuals’ quality of life, enabling independent living for longer periods, assisting people with disabilities, and supporting caregivers and medical staff. Among the technologies being explored in AAL, audio is increasingly used alone or alongside other modalities due to its interaction capabilities. Moreover, large language models (LLMs), enable enriched human-computer interactions. In this article, we present a system that leverages audio analysis in combination with LLMs in the context of AAL aiming at providing services such as cognitive assistance, medical follow-up or entertainment. Preliminary tests show promising results to promote the adoption of LLMs in AAL environments.

Keywords: Audio analysis · Ambient Assisted Living · Large Language Models · Context-aware systems · Cognitive Scenarios

1 Introduction

Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) environments enable healthier and more independent living for longer periods, providing assistance and support to users with specific medical conditions, as well as to caregivers and medical staff [5]. AAL exploits information flows between different actors, such as devices of the Internet of Things, medical information systems, and the users themselves. In this line, AAL systems can be conceptualised as cognitive systems to enable continuous learning and facilitate rapid adaptation to change, thereby achieving both sustainability and resilience. The concept of “cognitive”, based on theories of

Table 1. Most widely-explored enabling technologies in AAL.

Technology	Description
Internet of Things	Wearables and home sensors for continuous and remote monitoring of health, detecting falls, and providing real-time data to caregivers and healthcare providers.
Artificial Intelligence	Analyses data from IoT devices and combines them with other sources to provide insights and predictive analytics for timely interventions, personalising care, and improving decision-making processes in healthcare.
Robotics	Assists with daily activities, mobility, and social interaction, reducing the physical and emotional burden on caregivers and users.
Telemedicine and Telehealth	Enables ubiquitous consultations and monitoring, reducing healthcare costs and improving accessibility.
Cloud Continuum	Provides the infrastructure for storing and processing data collected from AAL devices, supporting real-time data analysis and integration with other healthcare systems according to different levels of requirements, enabling edge, fog, or cloud computations seamlessly.

networked learning, such as connectivism [16], is well documented for urban scenarios, *i.e.*, cognitive cities [11] and could be applied to other scenarios like AAL by deploying multiple collaborative agents and information systems. Numerous enabling technologies exist in the context of AAL, as summarised in Table 1. Audio and speech recognition are gaining momentum among such techniques and technologies, as it eases human interactions and provides further security and monitoring capabilities [6, 12, 9], namely physiological monitoring, emotion recognition, human activity recognition, fall detection, and human-machine conversations. Moreover, the use of audio enables *cognitive assistance*, defined as the interaction between the caregiver and the user in which the former provides assistive cues to which the assisted person replies with behaviours [1, 6].

This article focuses on the use of AI-based audio analysis as well as large language models (LLMs) to provide services in AAL, such as cognitive assistance, medical follow-up, entertainment and attention, to name a few. To leverage such a system, we rely on a pipeline that uses multiple technologies, as described in Section 2. We implement a proof of concept and a preliminary testing of its components in Section 3, and discuss the outcomes in Section 4. Finally, the article concludes in Section 5 denoting future research paths to explore.

2 Elements of our AAL system

We propose a cognitive AAL system that combines audio-based feature extraction and analysis, and the use of a LLM with the objective of providing a set of services via seamless human-computer interactions. The system, which could be set up as an independent AI agent, is composed by the Audio Analysis Unit, the Prompt Creation Unit, and the Response Renderer. The process is as follows:

- The Audio Analysis Unit captures the user’s query and extracts several features, aiming at identifying the user, detecting his/her emotion via voice-based sentiment analysis, and recognising the user’s query.
- The information extracted from the audio is sent to the Prompt Creation Unit, which combines the query with contextual information about the iden-

tified user, like emotion as well as other relevant data retrieved from a database with user’s profiles, to create an enriched prompt.

- The resulting prompt is used to query the LLM, enabling the correlation of events to follow-up the evolution of users.
- The response is sent to the user through the Response Renderer, which converts the text to speech. Additionally, the data of the whole process is stored as a report to be further analysed by caregivers and relatives, and to provide feedback to the user’s database.

Our system is aimed at providing, among others, the following services:

- *Audio Event Detection.* It consists of using microphones to sample and analyse environmental sounds aiming at detecting abnormal events such as falls, distress calls, or other unusual activities [3].
- *Speech Recognition.* We integrate automatic speech recognition for user interaction with AAL systems, allowing for hands-free control and providing a natural interface for users.
- *Audio Fingerprinting.* We identify both users and their emotions, improving the capabilities of monitoring systems.
- *Cognitive Assistance.* We can use the user’s information to enrich conversational agents. For instance, LLMs can process and detect user’s behavioural changes and understand their needs (*e.g.*, according to past experiences and profile information) and provide personalised solutions.

3 Experiments

We have implemented a proof of concept of our system and tested the different modules by using state of the art benchmarks to ensure their feasibility. The input audio is processed using Python libraries Librosa [13] and OpenAI Whisper [14], a pre-trained model with outstanding accuracy and multi-language capabilities [15], to extract the relevant data. Data used for profiling are stored in a vectorised repository to be transformed into tokens to enrich the LLM’s prompt. Such data can store personal information, medical information, and other particular relevant data to the user, such as previous queries and responses, enabling *e.g.*, the identification of behavioural changes. The LLM selected can have two different flavours, according to our privacy settings and functionality. More concretely, the LLM can be loaded locally from a repository such as Hugging Face according to the existing hardware or used via an API to query providers such as OpenAI. In this line, we have tested several quantised (quantisation is a method to map continuous infinite values to a smaller set of discrete finite values to optimise memory allocation among other tasks [7]) LLMs, specifically for their applicability in AAL environments with several prompts including conversations derived from the AnnoMI dataset [20].

Testing the entire system involves various benchmarks and tasks, each requiring different datasets and models, as seen in Table 2. For audio fingerprinting, we used the AOL 50 Speakers dataset, with XGBoost as the best-performing

model. For audio event detection, we ran a parallel process as a listener, allowing user-defined alert sounds, which will be further explored in future work. Speech recognition used OpenAI Whisper achieving perfect recognition on the emotion dataset used for audio profiling and sentiment analysis, based on four benchmarks from the dataset in [2]. In the case of conversational agents, we created a prompt with a synthetic context (*i.e.*, background information referring to the medical condition, medical prescriptions, and personal information) to be fed into the LLMs, and then we used questions extracted from AnnoMI dataset. While contextual information was perfectly used by all models, conversations were not fluent with the quantised LLaMa-based model tested [17]. In the case of GPT-4, we used OpenAI’s API with (gpt-4-0613) version in our experiments. The capabilities observed in GPT-4 were far more human, enabling specific tones that dynamically adapted to the conversation flow. Note that such benchmarks enable specific configurations and parameter setups to provide more accurate outcomes, as different LLMs with specific capabilities can be used. In addition, we assume that we generate reports which will be later analysed by the caregivers to assess the quality of the responses, the interactions, and other metrics relevant to the user’s condition. The latter, along with the input of the caregiver will be used to enrich the information of the profiles. Moreover, since we also aim to personalise outputs, we need to train the LLMs with behavioural information. As this entails further difficulties, such as specific data collection and the ethical and legal aspects involved, more advanced testing is left to future work. To summarise, each scenario has limitations that need to be assessed, but our pipeline is flexible enough to accommodate them.

Table 2. Summary of tests, outcomes and descriptions. MLP stands for multi-layer perceptron. Audio event detection did not use a benchmark due to its early stage.

Module	Benchmark	Model	Outcome Description
Audio Fingerprinting	AOL 50 Speakers [8]	XGBoost with “hist trees” and MLP	Best F1-score obtained by XGBoost was 0.97 in a multiclass classification setup.
Audio Event Detection	n/a	Librosa	We process the audio with Python libraries. We may raise an alert according to the audio signal shape and the decibels.
Speech Recognition	Pre-trained and tested on several benchmarks [15]	OpenAI Whisper	All audios from [2] were transcribed without errors by using an OpenAI’s Python library.
Audio Sentiment	Four audio Benchmarks [2]	MLP	We analysed the tone and sentiment of audio files. F1-score = 0.8.
Conversational Agent	Preliminary tests using AnnoMI dataset [20]	Quantised LLaMA 7B and GPT-4	The conversational functionalities were tested yet with some hallucinations.

4 Discussion

As described in Table 2, each of the modules of our proof of concept have been initially tested, obtaining promising outcomes.

While there is room for improvement, these preliminary results show that LLMs can be efficiently integrated into AAL environments. Moreover, our system considers the combination of emotional aspects and the temporary profiles of users to provide personalised responses, which enables more advanced interactions than recent works that only consider a subset of these aspects [18, 19].

Two particularly challenging aspects of our system are optimisation and the acquisition of information from patients to enable personalised services. While the latter can be eased by the participation of end users, optimisation can vary dynamically due to the use of, *e.g.*, cloud resources or the number of queries. Thus, we may define which models are used (*e.g.*, lightweight models can be used according to the hardware capabilities) to ensure the desired quality of service and increase adoption. The latter can be enhanced using Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) by integrating external information retrieval into the response generation process [4]. A particular aspect related to the above is training and fine-tuning by using resource-constrained devices to assess the system’s performance. Using a predefined set of elements, we aim to test the quality of LLM responses against evaluation measures such as readability and complexity, taking human judgement into account. Given their application in AAL, we expect LLMs to act as decision support systems; therefore, human involvement is crucial.

5 Conclusions

In this article, we presented a cognitive system to leverage audio-based AAL services by using a set of modules based on LLM and ML models. While the preliminary tests show promising results, we still have research paths to explore. These include testing more LLMs and defining a training setup for them to be tested in specific AAL contexts by using specific data inputs to be determined according to each application/functionality desired. For the latter, we aim to acquire relevant data to provide personalised responses and their assessment by the caregivers so that the impact can be assessed in real scenarios.

One of our aims is to provide the system with relevant input to be tested in real scenarios by understanding the user’s behaviour, characteristics and needs. The latter includes a behavioural analysis to tailor these agents to the user’s habits, needs, and preferences in a privacy-preserving way. For this, additional techniques and technology (*e.g.*, location-based devices, facial recognition) can be explored and combined with technologies such as smart mirrors, which enable health monitoring [10], and other IoT devices, such as cameras and temperature sensors, to provide a holistic response.

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References

1. Ayimdji Tekemetieu, A., et al.: From speech acts to assistance acts for cognitive assistance in ambient assisted living: How to nudge cognitively impaired people to act independently. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* **14**(9), 11767–11793 (2023)
2. Babko, D.: Speech Emotion Recognition (2021), <https://kaggle.com/datasets/dmitrybabko/speech-emotion-recognition-en>
3. Batista, E., Casino, F., Solanas, A.: On wandering detection methods in context-aware scenarios. In: 2016 7th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA). pp. 1–6. IEEE (2016)
4. Chen, J., et al.: Benchmarking Large Language Models in Retrieval-Augmented Generation. In: Proc. AAAI Conf. on Artificial Intelligence. pp. 17754–17762 (2024)
5. Cicirelli, G., et al.: Ambient Assisted Living: A Review of Technologies, Methodologies and Future Perspectives for Healthy Aging of Population. *Sensors* **21**(10), 3549 (2021)
6. Despotovic, V., et al.: Audio-based Active and Assisted Living: A review of selected applications and future trends. *Computers in Biology and Medicine* **149**, 106027 (2022)
7. Dettmers, T., et al.: QLORA: Efficient Finetuning of Quantized LLMs. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* **36** (2024)
8. Jain, V.: Speaker Recognition Audio Dataset (2023), <https://kaggle.com/datasets/vjcalling/speaker-recognition-audio-dataset>
9. Latif, S., et al.: Speech Technology for Healthcare: Opportunities, Challenges, and State of the Art. *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering* **14**, 342–356 (2021)
10. Lee, K., et al.: US Patent 10694988B2: System and method for detecting physiological state (2020)
11. Machin, J., et al.: Privacy and Security in Cognitive Cities: A Systematic Review. *Applied Sciences* **11**(10), 4471 (2021)
12. Martinez-Ballesté, A., et al.: An autonomous system to assess, display and communicate the pain level in newborns. In: Proc. Int. Symp. Medical Measurements and Applications. pp. 1–5 (2014)
13. McFee, B., et al.: librosa: Audio and Music Signal Analysis in Python. In: Proc. 14th Python in Science Conf. pp. 18–24 (2015)
14. OpenAI: Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision (2024), <https://github.com/openai/whisper>
15. Radford, A., , et al.: Robust Speech Recognition via Large-Scale Weak Supervision. In: 40th Int. Conf. Machine Learning. pp. 28492–28518 (2023)
16. Siemens, G.: Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning* **2**(1) (2005)
17. TheBloke: Llama 2 7B Chat - GGUF (2023), <https://huggingface.co/TheBloke/Llama-2-7B-Chat-GGUF>
18. Treder, M.S., et al.: Introduction to Large Language Models (LLMs) for dementia care and research. *Frontiers in Dementia* **3**, 1385303 (2024)
19. Wang, L., et al.: Integrating Large Language Models (LLMs) and Deep Representations of Emotional Features for the Recognition and Evaluation of Emotions in Spoken English. *Applied Sciences* **14**(9), 3543 (2024)
20. Wu, Z., et al.: Creation, Analysis and Evaluation of AnnoMI, a Dataset of Expert-Annotated Counselling Dialogues. *Future Internet* **15**(3), 110 (2023)